

Examining Study Habits as a Potential Mediator Between Time Management and Academic Achievement Among BS Office Administration Students at a State University in Cavite

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Date Submitted:

April 3, 2026

Date Accepted:

May 14, 2026

Date Published:

June 30, 2026

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.21055144

ABSTRACT

Academic achievement remains a critical indicator of student success in higher education, with time management and study habits frequently identified as important determinants of academic achievement. However, limited research has examined the mediating role of study habits in the relationship between time management and academic achievement among Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) students. This study investigated the levels of time management, study habits, and academic achievement and examined the direct and indirect relationships among these variables. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was employed involving 224 BSOA students from a state university in Cavite. Data were gathered using modified questionnaires and analysed by Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The measuring model was tested for reliability and

validity using Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, average variance extracted, and discriminant validity. The results indicated that the students' time management was at a good level, study habits at a moderate level, and academic achievement at an excellent level. The findings of the structural model showed that the study habits had a substantial impact on the academic and time management had a big impact on the academic achievement. But time management did not have any meaningful effect on the habits of study. In addition, study habits did not have a significant mediating effect between time management and academic achievement. The study shows that time management and study habits are independent predictors of academic achievement and that study habits do not mediate between time management and academic achievement. These results provide empirical data for the development of programs that attempt to increase students' academic achievement by improving their time management and study skills.

Keywords: *time management, study habits, academic achievement, BS Office Administration students, mediation*

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement continues to be an important indication of educational success and the development of human capital. It represents the extent to which students achieve learning objectives and acquire the information, skills, and competencies needed for academic advancement and future employment possibilities. Good academic achievement has been linked to better career opportunities, increased lifetime wages, and more social mobility

(Mutaufiq et al., 2025). While this learning is important, many students throughout the globe still struggle to attain the desired academic levels. In contemporary educational settings, students' learning habits and academic results are shaped by growing academic pressures, swift technology breakthroughs, and expanding learning modalities (Deng et al., 2022; Ma, 2023; Strom, 2021). Consequently, the determinants of academic achievement continue to be a key issue for educators, politicians, and academics.

International assessment evidence shows the shared issues experienced by students throughout education systems. OECD (2023) reported that only roughly 69% of students in participating nations obtained the minimal proficiency level for mathematics, while around 74% achieved the basic competency level for reading and science. The results suggest that a substantial number of learners still encounter challenges in fundamental academic abilities. Similarly, the Institute of Education Sciences (2023) stated that 44% of public-school learners in the United States were behind grade level in at least one subject while entering the 2023–2024 school year. In Europe, Siena et al. (2024) found that 25.4% of Italian university students experienced a decrease in their academic performance. Overall, our data imply that academic underperformance is still a pervasive international problem in the face of current educational reforms and initiatives.

This is especially troublesome in the context of Philippine education. There are recent instances of major learning problems among Filipino students. The student proficiency rates decline sharply from over 30% in Grade 3 to only 0.47% in Grade 12 (Senate of the Philippines, 2026). These results indicate that the fundamental skills acquired in the initial years of school are not always carried over as students go forward through the educational system. Additionally, international assessments have found that Filipino learners are among the lowest performing students in the world. For instance, the latest international assessment on education where the Philippines ranked 60th out of 62 countries that participated, which points out the continuing issues on student learning and the quality of education (Esquire Philippines, 2024).

Given these problems, academic achievement-linked elements have been extensively studied by researchers. Previous research has found time management, socioeconomic position, learning motivation, and self-regulated learning as major determinants of academic success (Faiza et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2025; Oroz et al., 2025). One of these elements that has been singled out is time management, a key competence that allows students to organize resources efficiently, prioritize academic assignments, and complete educational requirements. It has been established that study habits (i.e., learning routines and tactics such as focus, note-taking, reading comprehension, exam preparation, and anxiety management) increase learning efficiency and academic achievement. Good time management in theory helps students create favorable study habits that may result in better academic achievement. However, scientific research exploring these interrelationships is scarce and inconclusive.

There is a vast literature on academic achievement, yet certain gaps persist. First, several studies were carried out on time management, study habits, and academic achievement separately, and a limited study that explores the interaction among these factors in a unified explanatory framework. Second, previous studies have mostly adopted descriptive-correlational methodologies, which can identify relationships but offer little understanding of the processes influencing academic results (Calonia et al., 2023). Third, the current research has often concentrated on specific student demographics such as medical students and other specialized academic groups, which constrains the generalizability of the findings to other higher education environments. More crucially, there is a lack of studies that examine the mediating influence of study habits on the link between time management and academic achievement among students at public universities. This difference is more pronounced among the students of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration whose academic requirements call for good organizational and self-management abilities.

From a theoretical and practical point of view, filling these gaps is vital. Theoretically, by analyzing study habits as a mediating variable, a more complete knowledge of the effect of time management on academic achievement may be gained. From a practical standpoint, knowledge of the characteristics that contribute to academic achievement may help educators and administrators to design evidence-based interventions to improve student performance and learning outcomes.

Hence, the study was done to find out the link among time management, study habits, and academic achievement of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students in a state university. Specifically, it investigated the levels of time management, study habits, and academic achievement among students; established the association among these variables; and concluded whether study habits mediate the relationship between time management and academic achievement. The findings are intended to contribute to the expanding body of literature on student academic achievement and to give empirical information that can impact educational policies and student development programs in higher education institutions.

Literature Review

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is one of the main indicators of educational success and shows the capacity of students to achieve the intended learning goals. Studies have shown that academic success is affected by a mix of environmental, psychological, and behavioral variables. External elements such as classroom atmosphere, teacher support, and learning resources influence student engagement and performance (Gokpinar-Shelton & Pike, 2022). Similarly, internal characteristics such as motivation, emotional intelligence, and self-regulated learning have been shown to strongly affect academic achievement (Costa et al., 2024; Halimi et al., 2020). Additionally, there is evidence that students who participate in self-monitoring of their learning and employ good academic practices do better than their classmates (Estévez et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2024). Despite these findings, academic underachievement continues to be an issue, underscoring the need of examining behavioral aspects that might be improved through educational interventions.

Time Management and Academic Achievement

Time management has emerged as one of the most important predictors of academic success in higher education. It refers to the ability to plan, prioritize, and allocate time effectively to accomplish academic tasks and goals (Aeon et al., 2021; Patzak et al., 2025). Empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that students with effective time management skills achieve higher academic achievement because they are better able to organize learning activities, avoid procrastination, and maintain focus on academic responsibilities (Romero et al., 2023; Izzati Aufa et al., 2024). A recent meta-analysis by Liu et al. (2024) further confirmed that effective time management positively influences academic achievement, academic satisfaction, and self-efficacy. These findings suggest that students who effectively manage their time are more likely to achieve favorable academic outcomes.

Study Habits and Academic Achievement

Study habits are the usual practices or routines which students use to acquire, absorb and utilize information. They include note taking, reading comprehension, attentiveness, test preparation and anxiety control. Better academic achievement is consistently associated with strong study habits, since they help students to learn more thoroughly, recall knowledge better and engage more in academics (Aljaffer et al., 2024). Similarly, Wolters and Brady (2021) showed that students who actively monitored and regulated their learning activities reported better study habits and higher academic achievement. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that effective study habits can decrease academic stress and boost learning results (García-Ros et al., 2022). The results clearly show the relevance of study habits in helping students to achieve academic achievement.

Study Habits as a Mediating Variable

Emerging data suggests that study habits may be an important mediating factor of the relationship between time management and academic achievement. Time management also helps the students to develop consistent study plans, which allow them to allocate enough time for academic tasks and reduce procrastination, thereby promoting productive study behaviours (Fu et al., 2025; Patzak et al., 2025). In turn, students with good study habits demonstrate improved focus, better learning efficiency, and better academic success (Aljaffer et al., 2024). Previous

research has examined the effects of time management and study habits on academic achievement separately. Few research have looked at the mediating impact of study habits, notably among students at state universities. The gap implies the need for more research on the function of study habits as an explanation of the link between time management and academic achievement in higher education settings.

Hypotheses

Based on the existing literature, the researchers hypothesized that:

- H1: Time management significantly influences academic achievement.
- H2: Time management significantly influences study habits.
- H3: Study habits significantly influence academic achievement.
- H4: Study habits mediate the relationship between time management and academic achievement.

METHODS

Research Design

The study used quantitative, descriptive-correlational methodology in determining the mediating influence of study habits on the link between time management and academic achievement of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA) students. The study used Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to investigate predicted correlations among the latent components and also test direct and indirect effects.

Population and Sampling

The target population consisted of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students enrolled at a State University in Cavite during the second semester of Academic Year 2025–2026. The required sample size was determined using Slovin's formula, since the total population is known, with a 5% margin of error, resulting in a minimum sample of 224 respondents. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select eligible respondents based on predefined inclusion criteria.

Research Instrument

The data were acquired using an adopted questionnaire with four sections: demographic information, academic achievement, time management, and study habits. Time management was examined using items derived from Oroz et al. (2025), and study habits were assessed using the instrument created by Giray and Ballado (2025). The academic achievement was judged using the General Weighted Average (GWA) of the students. In data analysis, reverse coding was carried out such that the interpretation of results was consistent because lower GWA values mean better academic success, and higher scores mean higher academic achievement.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were obtained from online survey using Google Forms. After gaining the required approval, the survey link was sent to eligible BSOA students. The participants were informed about the aim of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, confidentiality, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation, were used to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents and the levels of time management and study habits.

To test the proposed model, PLS-SEM was performed. The measurement model was evaluated using indicator loadings, Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) to establish reliability and validity.

Table 1. *Convergent Validity and Reliability of the Constructs*

Construct / Indicators	Outer Loadings	Composite Reliability	AVE
Academic Achievement (GWA – single indicator)	1.000	—	—
Study Habits ($\alpha = 0.880$)		0.900	0.567
Test Anxiety Management	0.736		
Concentration	0.701		
Note Taking	0.776		
Reading Comprehension	0.820		
Reading Speed	0.705		
Test Preparation and Test Taking	0.841		
Writing Skills	0.850		
Time Management ($\alpha = 0.796$)		0.906	0.829
Management Tools	0.930		
Objectives and Priorities	0.890		

The measurement model results in Table 1 show that all constructs have excellent convergent validity and internal consistency reliability. The outer loadings of the indicators are between 0.701 and 0.930, which are higher than the required 0.70 (Hair et al., 2021), showing the indicators are good representations of the constructs they intend to measure. The Cronbach’s alpha for study habits was 0.880, and the composite reliability was 0.900, while the Cronbach’s alpha for time management was 0.796 and the composite reliability was 0.906.

These scores are above the acceptable level of 0.70, showing strong internal consistency reliability. Convergent validity was established through the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values of the study habits (0.567) and time management (0.829) which are above the minimum permissible threshold of 0.50 and indicate that the constructs explain an adequate amount of variance in their indicators. Academic achievement was measured using a single indicator (General Weighted Average), which had an outside loading of 1.000. The measurement model as a whole displays adequate reliability and validity, suggesting its suitability for further structural model study.

Table 2. *Discriminant validity – Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Matrix*

	Academic Achievement	Study Habits	Time Management
Academic Achievement			
Study Habits	0.154		
Time Management	0.061	0.197	

From the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) analysis in Table 2, all values were below the recommended threshold of 0.85 (Henseler et al., 2015), showing that discriminant validity among the constructs was good. Specifically, the HTMT values for academic achievement and study habits (0.154), academic achievement and time management (0.061) and study habits and time management (0.197) indicate that the categories are empirically diverse and assess different theoretical ideas. This indicates the measurement model has good discriminant validity, which supports the appropriateness of the measurement model for further examination of the structural model.

Table 3. *Collinearity Statistics (VIF)*

	VIF
Academic Achievement	1.000
Study Habits – Test Anxiety Management	1.806
Study Habits – Concentration	1.522
Study Habits - Note Taking	1.909

Study Habits - Reading Comprehensive	2.277
Study Habits – Reading Speed	1.524
Study Habits – Test Preparation and Test Taking	2.291
Study Habits - Writing Skills	2.078
Time Management – Management Tools	1.777
Time Management – Objectives and Priorities	1.777

In Table 3, the findings of collinearity assessment using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) are presented, and all values range from 1.000 to 2.291. These values are below the threshold value of 5.0 as indicated by Hair et al. (2021) and more conservatively below 3.3, indicating that multicollinearity is not a problem in the structural model. The indicators of study habits and time management indicate acceptable degrees of independence, indicating that each construct makes a unique contribution to the model without overlap or distortion. This justifies the appropriateness of the dataset for subsequent structural equation modelling research.

The indirect effect of time management on academic achievement via study habits was tested to assess the mediating role of study habits. Statistical significance was defined at the 0.05 level.

Ethical Considerations

The study was performed in compliance with ethical criteria generally accepted for research with human subjects. All respondents provided informed consent before participating. Participants were informed of the goal of the study, the processes involved, the voluntary nature of their participation, the steps taken to ensure anonymity, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. No personally identifiable information was collected and all responses were kept strictly confidential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Respondents' Time Management

Table 4 presents the level of time management among BS Office Administration students in terms of objectives and priorities and management tools.

Table 4. *Level of Respondents' Time Management*

Item	M	SD	Scaled Response	Verbal Interpretation
Objective and Priorities	3.65	0.727	Often	Good
Management Tools	3.28	0.848	Sometimes	Fair
Grand Mean	3.47	0.788	Often	Good

Scoring System: 4:21 –5.0= Always (Excellent), 3.41 –4.20= Often (Good), 2.61 –3.40= Sometimes (Fair), 1.81 –2.60= Rarely (Poor), 1.00 –1.80= Never (Very Poor)

The mean score of 3.47 (SD = 0.788) suggests that the respondents exhibit a generally high level of time management, which is read as “Often” and described as “Good.” This means that generally, students have similar time management behaviors in managing academic tasks, but differences exist in particular aspects.

The results showed that the average score of students was 3.65 (SD=0.727) in terms of objectives and priorities, which was classified as “Often” with a “Good” level. This shows that students as a whole are successful in setting academic goals, prioritizing, and allocating their time according to academic needs.

The findings suggest that students are generally more proficient in goal setting and prioritization than in other aspects of time management. This behavior indicates they are able to recognize critical academic work and

manage their responsibilities successfully. This is in line with the findings of Das and Bera (2021), who highlighted that prioritization and systematic planning help immensely in better academic achievement among students by boosting concentration and reducing task overload.

In contrast, management tools obtained a lower mean score of 3.28 (SD = 0.848), interpreted as “Sometimes” and described as “Fair.” This indicates that students only occasionally use structured tools such as planners, calendars, and digital applications to organize their academic tasks. The higher standard deviation compared to objectives and priorities also suggests greater variability in students’ use of time management tools.

This research indicates that students have good cognitive planning skills but are less consistent in applying external tools to help them organize their time. The difference may reflect reliance on informal or internal planning strategies rather than formal time management methods. Wilson et al. (2021) found that students who use time management tools more often are more organized and do better academically because these tools improve the efficiency of monitoring, scheduling, and performing assignments.

Level of Respondents’ Study Habits

The results in Table 5 show that the level of respondents’ study habits has a total grand mean of 3.14 (SD = 0.806), which is interpreted as “Sometimes (Good)” indicating that students have average study habits that are observed but not in all areas of study. This indicates that while learners demonstrate functioning academic activities, the consistent use of efficient study strategies is absent and can impact the overall learning efficiency and academic achievement.

Table 5. Level of Respondents’ Study Habits

Item	M	SD	Scaled Response	Verbal Interpretation
Concentration	3.03	0.769	Sometimes	Fair
Note taking	3.47	0.735	Often	Good
Reading Comprehension	3.29	0.81	Sometimes	Fair
Test preparation and test taking	3.09	0.877	Sometimes	Fair
Reading Speed	2.97	0.677	Sometimes	Fair
Writing Skills	3.12	0.852	Sometimes	Fair
Test Anxiety Management	3.04	0.919	Sometimes	Fair
Grand Mean	3.14	0.806	Sometimes	Good

Scoring System: 4:21 –5.0= Always (Excellent), 3.41 –4.20= Often (Good), 2.61 –3.40= Sometimes (Fair), 1.81 –2.60= Rarely (Poor), 1.00 –1.80= Never (Very Poor)

The mean score for concentration was 3.03 (SD = 0.769), which was interpreted as Sometimes (Fair). This shows that students are sometimes able to maintain focus throughout academic work but are often distracted. In keeping with current evidence, decreased attentional control is often related to fragmented study environments and higher cognitive load, both of which have negative implications for academic engagement and learning retention (Svartdal et al., 2021).

The respondents indicated the highest mean of 3.47 (SD = 0.735) for note-taking, which was evaluated as Often (Good). This suggests that students more often than not use organized note-taking procedures, which show a somewhat greater metacognitive learning practice than other areas. Active learning and cognitive organization are promoted by effective note-taking, which has been shown in empirical research to improve academic attainment (Voyer et al., 2022).

When it comes to reading comprehension, the respondents' average score was 3.29 (SD = 0.810) categorized as Sometimes (Fair). This shows that students are able to understand complicated academic writings at a functional level, but are not always able to critically analyze and synthesize these texts. Reading comprehension is an important academic skill that can greatly affect higher-order thinking and subject mastery (Walck-Shannon et al., 2021). Active reading practices can dramatically enhance learning results.

On the aspect of test preparation and test taking, the respondents had a mean of 3.09 (SD = 0.877), which is interpreted as Sometimes (Fair). This suggests inconsistent engagement in systematic review and preparation procedures for evaluation. Such diversity reflects reliance on non-structured or short-term study practices, which may impede long-term retention and performance. Previous research has shown that self-regulated learning and organized preparation are key to academic achievement and the reduction of performance-related anxiety (Walck-Shannon et al., 2021).

Finally, the respondents had a mean of 3.04 (SD = 0.919), which is translated as Sometimes (Fair) in managing test anxiety. This means that students have moderate degrees of anxiety while being assessed, yet have the ability to regulate emotional responses generally. However, when exam anxiety is unresolved, it can impede cognitive functioning, weaken concentration, and negatively impact academic achievement. Good coping strategies and preparation methods are regularly connected with better emotional management and academic results (Myers et al., 2021).

Level of Respondents' Academic Achievement

Table 6. *Level of Respondent's Academic Achievement*

Item	M	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Academic Achievement	4.37	0.365	Excellent

Scoring System: 4:21 –5.0= Excellent, 3.41 –4.20= Good, 2.61 –3.40= Fair, 1.81 –2.60= Poor, 1.00 –1.80= Very Poor.

As shown in Table 6, the respondents' mean academic achievement score is 4.37 (SD=0.365), which is defined as "Excellent". This means that BS Office Administration students generally demonstrate high levels of academic achievement based on their GWA. This result demonstrates that the respondents are capable of fulfilling and surpassing the academic standards of their program. This indicates good learning outcomes and good academic engagement.

The low standard deviation (SD=0.365) shows little variation among respondents; most students have similar great academic achievement. This uniformity shows that academic success is quite similar in the group with minor variation in the GWA results. Such uniformity may be due to the same academic standards, similar learning environments and similar exposure to instructional methodologies in the program.

More generally, the outcome is indicative of a solid academic body where students display consistency in their academic effort. This is in line with the findings in recent literature on higher education, indicating that academic achievement is highly related to students' motivation, learning techniques, and self-regulated learning practices (Costa et al., 2024). All these variables together lead to the university students' consistently high levels of academic achievement and achievement.

Relationship Between Variables

The results of PLS-SEM using bootstrapping with 10,000 resamples are presented in Table 7, showing the structural relationships among the variables. Hypotheses were evaluated based on path coefficients (β), t-statistics, p-values, and effect size (f^2) at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 7. *Path coefficient*

Hypothesis	Path	β	t-statistics	p-values	Effect Size (f^2)	Remarks
H1	Time Management > Academic Achievement	0.165	2.137	0.033	0.027	Accepted
H2	Time Management > Study Habits	0.017	0.263	0.792	0.000	Not Accepted

H3	Study Habits > Academic Achievement	0.206	2.604	0.009	0.045	Accepted
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* $p < 0.05$ (significant); $p > 0.05$ (non-significant)

For H1: Time Management \rightarrow Academic Achievement, the data demonstrate a positive and significant link ($\beta = 0.165$, $t = 2.137$, $p = 0.033$, $f^2 = 0.027$) and this hypothesis is accepted. This means that proper time management helps students attain better academic results. Cohen's criteria point to a minor effect size, but the findings imply that students with good time management skills are better at organizing academic work, meeting deadlines and allocating enough time for studying, which in turn promotes academic success. The result is consistent with Das and Bera (2021) who underlined the importance of time management in improving students' academic achievement.

In contrast, H2: Time Management \rightarrow Study Habits was found to be non-significant ($\beta = 0.017$, $t = 0.263$, $p = 0.792$, $f^2 = 0.000$) and hence the hypothesis was rejected. This means there is no direct effect of time management on the formation of study habits of the responders. The low effect size further supports the lack of meaningful association. This could mean that study habits could be more influenced by other aspects such as intrinsic motivation, self-regulation, learning environment and personal discipline and not time management alone. However, this finding is inconsistent with the findings of Bhattacharya et al. (2022) who found that time management can positively affect students' study discipline and habits.

For H3: Study Habits \rightarrow Academic Achievement, the analysis showed a positive and significant connection ($\beta = 0.206$, $t = 2.604$, $p = 0.009$, $f^2 = 0.045$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. This suggests that students who have better study habits likely to have higher academic achievement. The effect size is minor, but it does show that regularly engaging in structured learning behaviors like regular review, effective note-taking, and methodical exam preparation can be a major contributor to academic achievement. This finding is in line with that of Muhammad et al. (2023), who stress the importance of good study habits to the academic success of students.

In sum, the structural model reveals that both time management and study habits directly contribute to academic achievement, although the relationship between time management and study habits is not substantial. These results indicate that behavioral learning methods (study habits) and organizational abilities (time management) have more direct benefits on academic achievement than the others. Although statistically significant, the effect sizes indicate that time management and study habits explain only a small proportion of academic achievement, suggesting that other factors contribute substantially to academic achievement.

Mediating Role of Study Habits

The mediation analysis tested the indirect effect of Time Management on Academic Achievement through Study Habits using PLS-SEM with bootstrapping procedures. The results, presented in Table 8, show that the indirect relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($\beta = 0.034$, $t = 1.731$, $p = 0.083$), leading to the rejection of Hypothesis 4 (H4). This indicates that Study Habits do not significantly mediate the relationship between Time Management and Academic Achievement among the respondents.

Table 8. *Specific Indirect Effects (Mediation)*

Hypothesis	Path	β	t-statistics	p-values	Remarks
H4	Time Management > Study Habits > Academic Achievement	0.034	1.731	0.083	Not Accepted

* $p < 0.05$ (significant); $p > 0.05$ (non-significant)

However, the indirect effect is not significant suggesting that while Time Management and Study Habits contribute separately to academic outcomes, Study Habits do not serve as a causative connection between Time Management and Academic Achievement. In other words, the effect of Time Management on academic

achievement appears to be independent rather than mediated by improvements in study habits. This suggests that other psychological and contextual characteristics, such as motivation, self-discipline, cognitive engagement and learning environment, are more important in determining academic achievement.

This conclusion is in line with Broadbent and Poon (2021) who stressed that academic progress is dependent on many self-regulated learning mechanisms and individual learner characteristics rather than a single mediating pathway. Although the hypothesized mediating role was not validated, the findings underscore the relevance of both Time Management and Study Habits as separate influences on academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to determine the level of time management, study habits and academic achievement of BS Office Administration students of Cavite State University–Indang Main Campus and to find out the link among these factors including the mediating function of study habits.

The results showed that the level of time management of the respondents was good in general, especially in setting objectives and priorities, while the use of management tools was moderate. Also, the respondents had moderate study habits, with note-taking being the most prominent study behavior, while reading speed is the least rated. Despite these moderate study habits, the students achieved an excellent degree of academic achievement, showing consistently high academic achievement among the sample.

The structural model indicated that time management had a significant and positive impact on academic achievement. Moreover, study habits had significant effect on academic achievement implying that students that have good time management and study well are likely to perform better academically. However, time management was not a significant factor in study habits. This indicates that the formation of study habits may be dependent on factors other than students' ability to manage time.

Furthermore, the mediation analysis showed that study habits did not significantly mediate the relationship between time management and academic achievement. Time management has therefore a primarily direct effect on academic achievement, not an indirect one through study habits. Thus, while both time management and study habits independently contribute to academic success, study habits do not serve as a significant mechanism linking time management to academic achievement among the respondents.

In general, the study found out that time management and study habits are major drivers of academic achievement among BS Office Administration students. However, academic achievement seems to be affected by a wider range of personal, behavioral and contextual characteristics than the variables considered in this study. The findings provide empirical information that can be used to build treatments and academic support programs to improve students' time management abilities, study practices, and academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is proposed that the College of Economics, Management and Development Studies expand programs and activities that encourage good time management and study skills of BS Office Administration students. Faculty members can include structured learning tactics such as goal setting, note-taking procedures, and testing strategies into their classroom activities to improve students' academic achievement.

Students are encouraged to use tools such as planners, calendars, and digital tools for time management to increase organization and productivity. They also need to acquire more consistent study habits, especially with regard to fast reading, focus, and test preparation.

Future researchers might study other aspects that impact academic achievement such as motivation, self-discipline, learning environment, and self-regulated learning, to provide a more comprehensive picture of students' academic success.

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